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**QATOR ORALARIGA ISHLOV BERUVCHI TISHLI
YUMSHATKICHLI QURULMA**

Xasanov Ibrohim Subxonovich

– “TIQXMMI” MTU Buxoro tabiiy resurslarini boshqarish instituti o’quv
ishlari bo’yicha prorektori, texnika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Isakov Zafarjon Shuxrat o’g’li

- “Gidromelioratsiya ishlarining texnika va texnologiyalari” kafedrası tayanch
doktoranti Email: zafar.isakov.95@mail.ru

Yusupova Oynura Mehriddinovna

- “TIQXMMI” MTU Buxoro tabiiy resurslarni boshqarish instituti talabasi.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada g’o’zani sug’orishdan keyin g’o’za qator oralariga ishlov beruvchi tishli yumshatkichli qurulma haqida bayon etilgan. Maqolada g’o’za qator oralariga ishlov beruvchi tishli yumshatkichli qurulmaning umumiy tuzilishi, ishlash tartibi to’g’risida so’z borgan.

Kalit so’zlar: tishli yumshatkich, zamonaviy texnika va texnologiyalar, stoyka, qishloq xo’jaligi, planka.

**УСТРОЙСТВО СМЯГЧЕНИЯ ШЕСТЕРНИ, РАБОТАЮЩЕЕ
МЕЖДУ РЯДАМИ.**

Аннотация: В статье описано устройство с зубчатым смягчителем, обрабатывающее хлопок между рядами после полива. В статье рассказывается об общем устройстве и порядке работы зубчатого умягчительного устройства, работающего между рядами хлопка.

Ключевые слова: зубчатая смягчитель, современное оборудование и технологии, стойки, сельское хозяйство, планка.

GEAR SOFTENING DEVICE OPERATING BETWEEN THE ROWS

Abstract: The article describes the device with a toothed softener that processes cotton between rows after watering. The article talks about the general structure and working order of the toothed softener device that works between rows of cotton.

Key words: toothed softener, modern equipment and technologies, rack, agriculture, plank.

O’zbekistonning dunyo paxta ishlab chiqaradigan mamlakatlar ichida 6 o’rinda turadi. Mamlakatimiz aholisining turmush darajasi, uning moddiy farovonligi qishloq xo’jaligidagi iqtisodiy islohotlarning borishiga uni rivojlantirishning tezkorligi va samaradorligiga bog’liqdir. Shu o’rinda fermer xo’jaliklari egalari yerni asrab-avaylab, unga o’z vaqtida va sifatli ishlov berib, barcha agrotexnik tadbirlarga rioya qilish to’kin hayotining muhim omilidir [1].

Mamlakatimiz qishloq xo’jaligi mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish qishoqdagi infratuzilmalarni rivojlantirish bilan uzviy bog’liqdir. Zero, qishloqlardagi iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy infratuzilmani sifat jihatdan zamon talablari darajasiga ko’tarish bugun mamlakat rivojiga ijobiy ta’sir etmasdan qolmaydi.

Prezidentimiz ta’kidlaganidek, qishloq iqtisodiyotida va ijtimoiy

turmushda, binobarin, siyosatda ham shundan bir bo'g'ingki, shu bo'g'in orqali butun respublika farovonlik va to'kin-sochinlikka erishadi. Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarishni esa sug'oriladigan yerlarsiz tasavvur qilish qiyin, chunki biz hosilimizning 90% dan ortig'ini sug'oriladigan yerlardan olamiz. Shu boisdan ham irrigatsiya va yerlarning meliorativ holatini yaxshilash muammolari biz uchun hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega. Darhaqiqat, O'zbekiston keng qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarish kompleksiga ixtisoslashgan davlat bo'lganligi bois, avvalambor, yerlarning meliorativ holati va unumdorlik darajasi hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega hisoblanadi. Yerlarning hosildorligi esa asosan, ularning sug'orilishi va asrab-avaylanishi bilan uzviy bog'liqdir. Bu borada davlatimiz tomonidan mutsaqillikning ilk kunlaridayoq ham huquqiy, ham amaliy chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirib kelinmoqda [2].

O'zbekiston Respublikasi prezidenti Sh.Mirziyoyevning "Qishloq xo'jaligining texnik jihozlanish darajasini yanada oshirish borasidagi qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida"gi PQ-3459-sonli qarorining ijrosini ta'minlash borasida respublikamiz qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash, fermer xo'jaliklarining ekinlardan oladigan qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari hosildorligini oshirish uchun zamonaviy ilm-fan va texnika yutuqlaridan samarali foydalanishni nazarda tutadigan zamonaviy texnika va texnologiyalarni qo'llash, mavjudlarini takomillashtirishga yo'naltirilgan keng qamrovli ilmiy va innovatsion ishlar olib borilmoqda.

Bugungi kunda g'o'za qator oralariga sug'orish ishlari amalga oshirilgandan keyin ishlov berish ishlari faqatgina kultuvator orqali ishlov beriladi. Ammo bu g'o'za qator oralariga to'liq ishlov bera olmaydi. Natijada sug'orilgan g'o'za qator oralari ma'lum vaqt o'tgandan keyin yerning namligi kundan kun kamayib borish natijasida g'o'za qator oralarida turli xildagi yoriqlar paydo bo'ladi. Bu esa o'z navbatida birinchidan g'o'zaning ildiz tizimiga, ikkinchidan yer yuzidan suvning tez bug'lanishiga va yana tezroq sug'orish ishlar kompleksini amalga oshirishni taqazo etadi. Bu esa o'z navbatida suvning ko'p yo'qotilishiga olib keladi. Biz yuqoridagi manashu muammoni o'rgangan holda go'za qator oralariga ishlov beruvchi tishli yumshatkichli qurulmani taklif etmoqdamiz.

1-rasm. Qator oralariga ishlov beradigan tishli yumshatkichning konstruktiv sxemasi:

1-bo'ylama brus; 2-ko'ndalang brus; 3, 4-rostlovchi mexanizm;

5, 6-mahkamlovchi qulf; 7-ustun; 8-sharnir; 9-planka; 10-prujina; 11-tish.

Yuqoridagi rasmda taklif etilayotgan qator oralariga ishlov beruvchi tishli yumshatkichning konstruktiv sxemasi ko'rsatib o'tilgan. Qator oralariga ishlov beruvchi tishli yumshatkichda bo'ylama holda turgan brus 1 hamda unga ko'ndalang holda mahkamlangan brus 2 lar bo'lib, bo'ylama brus 1 old tomonidan pastga perpendikulyar holatda ustunga 7 o'rnatilgan. Sharnir 8 ustunga 7 qo'zg'aluvchan qilib mahkamlangan, ustun 7 esa bo'ylama brus 1 ga mahkamlovchi qulf 6 orqali mahkamlanadi. Taklif etilayotgan tishli yumshatkichning orqa tomoni esa bo'ylama brusga perpendikulyar ravishda mahkamlangan brus 2 larga mahkamlanadi. Bunda ko'ndalang brus 2 lar va parallel ravishda o'rnatilgan planka 9 lar orasiga yumshatkichlarning ish jarayonida vertikal burchagini dala notekisligiga mos holda o'zgarishini ta'minlovchi prujinali mexanizm 10 tashkil topgan, bir tekislikda tish 11 lar mahkamlangan 1 juft planka 3, 4 qamrov kengligi rostlanadigan qilib joylashtirilgan va 1 juft planka 9 larga birlashtirilgan. Bu yerda planka 9 lar sharnirli holatda mahkamlangan va ularni ko'ndalang brus 2 larga ustun 7 bog'lab turadi hamda rostlovchi mexanizm 3, 4 yordamida planka 9 lar bo'ylama va qamrov kengliklari rostlanadi. Qurilmada tuproqqa ishlov berish chuqurligi va qamrov kengligi planka 9 larni alohida vertikal hamda burchak ostidagi holatini o'zgartirish orqali rostlanadi.

G'ozga qator oralariga ishlov beruvchi tishli yumshatkich ishni boshlashdan oldin ishlov berish chuqurligi va qamrov kengligiga bog'liq holda tishli

yumshatkich rostanadi. Ishlov berish chuqurligi rostlovchi mexanizm 3, 4 dagi rezbali brikma yordamida planka 9 larni vertikal joylashtirish orqali amalga oshiriladi. Ishlov berishni qamrov kengligi planka 9 larni sharnir 8 atrofida surish va ko'ndalang bruslar 2 da turuvchi ustun 7 larni holatini o'zgartirish orqali amalga oshiriladi

2 – rasm. G'o'za qator oralariga ishlov beradigan tishli yumshatkichning agregatlangan holda ishlash jarayoni

Qurilmada planka 9 larni har birini alohida holatda rostlash imkoniyati mavjud. Tishlar mahkamlangan 1 juft planka va qamrov kengligi rostlanuvchi planka 3, 4 larni chuqurlikka rostlash imkoniyatini yaratadi, yumshatkichlarning ish jarayonida vertikal burchagini dala notekisligiga mos holda o'zgarishini ta'minlovchi prujinali mexanizm 10 dan tashkil topgan bu bizga qurilma bilan tuproqqa ishlov berish sifatini oshiradi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020 yil 29 dekabrda Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi. Xalq so'zi 2020 yil 30 dekabr № 276 son.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Qishloq xo'jaligi ilmiy-ishlab chiqarish markazi va O'zbekiston Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti ilmiy-tadqiqot instituti tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan 2016-2020 yillarga mo'ljallangan namunaviy texnologik xarita. T. 2016 y.
3. Sh. J. Imomov, [J. U. Ruzikulov](#), S. S. Kurbanbayev, H. S. Safarov, K. S. Sobirov, and Z. Sh. Isakov "Technological process of provisional dig a ditch", Proc. SPIE 12296, International Conference on Remote Sensing of the Earth: Geoinformatics, Cartography, Ecology, and Agriculture (RSE 2022), 1229600 (6 July 2022); <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2642980>
4. Energy-saving device for temporary ditch digging I S Hasanov1, J U Ruzikulov1, F A Ergashov1, M J Toshmurodova1 and M R Sotlikova1 Published under licence by IOP Publishing Ltd [IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, Volume 868, International Conference on Agricultural Engineering and Green Infrastructure Solutions \(AEGIS 2021\) 12th-14th May 2021, Tashkent, Uzbekistan](#)Citation I S Hasanov et al 2021 IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci. 868 012091DOI 10.1088/1755-1315/868/1/012091
5. Ruzikulov Jasur Uktam ugli, Kurbanbayev Sindorbek Sarvarbek ugli, Nasrullayev Alpomish Anvarjon ugli, Safarov Xusniddin Sirojiddin ugli, Research on the establishment of an improved temporary ditch production device, Galaxy international interdisciplinary research journal (GIIRJ), Volume 9, Issue 11, November, 2021
6. Ruzikulov Jasur Uktam ugli, Isakov Zafarjon Shuxrat ugli, Qurbonboyev Sindorbek Sarvarbek ugli, Ruzikulova Dilnoza Uktamovna, Xusinov Sarvarbek Nodirbek ugli. (2022). INCREASING THE WORKING PRODUCTIVITY OF THE CASE 1150 L BULLDOZER BY IMPROVING THE WORKING EQUIPMENT. Neo Science Peer Reviewed Journal, 4,

<https://tiame66.uz>

<https://uz-conference.com>

- 87–90. Retrieved from <https://www.neojournals.com/index.php/nsprj/article/view/83> .
7. Imomov Shavkat Jakhonovich, Murodov Tohir Faxriddin ugli, Isakov Zafarjon Shuxrat ugli, Ochilov Nuriddinjon zokirovich, Iskandarov Johongir Ochil ugli, & Ruziqulova Dilnoza Uktamovna. (2022). LOCAL FERTILIZER MACHINE WITH AUGER. Neo Science Peer Reviewed Journal, 4, 91–93. Retrieved from <https://www.neojournals.com/index.php/nsprj/article/view/84>
8. Ruziqulov , J. ., Kurbonboyev, S. ., Xusinov, S., & Ruziqulova , D. . (2023). IMPROVEMENT OF THE SCRAPER WORK EQUIPMENT AND IMPROVING ITS EFFICIENCY. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research,3(1 Part 4), 12–16. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/8935>
9. P.G.Hikmatov, J.U.Ruzikulov, O.S.Sayidov, Ruziqulova Dilnoza Uktamovna , [IMPROVED MACHINE FOR SPREADING AND COMPACTING ROAD CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS.](https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibast/article/-view/2020), *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology: Vol. 3 No. 6 (2023): International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology* <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibast/article/-view/2020>
10. P.G.Hikmatov, J.U.Ruzikulov , O.S.Sayidov, Ruzikulova Dilnoza Uktamovna , [SELECTION OF AN AUGER DEVICE FOR A MACHINE FOR SPREADING AND COMPACTING IMPROVED ROAD CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS](https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibast/article/view/2009) , *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology: Vol. 3 No. 6 (2023): International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology* <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibast/article/view/2009>
11. U.I.Khasanov, A.A.Jurayev, J.U.Ruziqulov, X.Maratov, & D.U.Ro'ziqulova. (2023). PORTABLE DRIP IRRIGATION SYSTEM. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(4), 184–188. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10184611>
12. A.A.Jo'rayev, J.O'.Ro'ziqulov, Sh.Ergashov, & D.O'.Ro'ziqulova. (2023). Improvement of single-bucket hydraulic excavator working equipment to prevent violation of their design parameters when cleaning concrete channels. technical science research in uzbekistan, 1(4), 251–254. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10195687>
13. J.U.Ruzikulov, D.U.Ruzikulova, U.F.Khusenov. ENERGY-SAVING DEVICE FOR TEMPORARY DITCH PRODUCTION FRANCE international scientific-online conference: “SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM” PART 18, 5thOCTOBER <https://interonconf.org/index.-php/fra/article/view/7258/6260>
14. Рузикулов Жасур Уктам угли, Хусенов Ўлмас Файзулло угли, Рузикулова Дилноза Уктамовна. Теоритические предпосылки определения тяглого сопротивления канавокопателя с дисковыми ножами. Finland, Helsinki international scientific online conference “Sustainability of education socio-economic science theory” <http://www.interonconf.net>
15. U.I.Khasanov, A.A.Jurayev, J.U.Ruziqulov, X.Maratov, & D.U.Ro'ziqulova. (2023). PORTABLE DRIP IRRIGATION SYSTEM. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(4), 184–188. Retrieved from <http://mjstjournal.com/index.php/mjst/article/view/336>
16. A.A.Jo'rayev, J.O'.Ro'ziqulov, Sh.Ergashov, & D.O'.Ro'ziqulova. (2023). IMPROVEMENT OF SINGLE-BUCKET HYDRAULIC EXCAVATOR WORKING EQUIPMENT TO PREVENT VIOLATION OF THEIR DESIGN PARAMETERS WHEN CLEANING CONCRETE CHANNELS. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(4), 251–254. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/~niverta1/index.php/tsru/article/view/2768>
17. J.Sh.Fazliev., Sh.M.Tojiev., Sh.D.Khalikov. (2024). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 504–509. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/107>
18. I.J.Xudayev, I.J.Xudayev, & Sh.M.Tojiyev. (2024). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN

- HOSIL QILINGAN EKTRANLI EGATLARDAN G'O'ZANI SUG'ORISH
TEKNOLOGIYASI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 514–519. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/109>
19. Fazliyev, Z. S., Shokhimardonova, N. S., Sobirov, F. T., Ravshanov, U. K., & Baratov, S. S. (2014). Technology of the drip irrigation use in gardens and vineyards. *The Way of Science*, 56.
20. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). INTEGRATIV YONDASHUV ASOSIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY TEKNOLOGIYALARI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 945–950. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/195>
21. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). TEXNIKA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI AXBOROT TA'LIM MUHITIDA O'QITISHNING MUHIM YO'NALISHLARI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 938–944. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/194>
22. Ikrom, I. (2023). KASBIY TAYYORGARLIKNING RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI BO'YICHA PEDAGOGIK TAJRIBA-SINOV ISHLARI NATIJALARINING TAHLILI. In *Uz-Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 626-633).
23. Shaxrilloevich, I. I. (2023). DIDACTIC CONDITIONS FOR THE PREPARATION OF STUDENTS OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH. *Academia Repository*, 4(10), 142-145.
24. Саримсаков, М. М. (2023, May). СПОСОБЫ ПОЛИВА И УРОЖАЙНОСТЬ ИНТЕНСИВНЫХ ЯБЛОНЕВЫХ САДОВ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 14, pp. 173-175).
25. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш., & Шохимарданова, Н. Ш. (2024). БОҒЛАРНИ ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШДА ТУПРОҚ-ГРУНТ НАМЛАНИШ КОНТУРИНИ АНИҚЛАШ УСЛУБИ. *IMRAS*, 7(2), 34-38.
26. Sadirovich, S. N. (2022). The Significance of Problem Situation Assignments in Teaching the Science of Machine Details. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 3(8), 30-32.
27. Shodiev, N. S. (2022). USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PREPARING ENGINEERING STUDENTS FOR PROJECT-CONSTRUCTION ACTIVITY. *Экономика и социум*, (10-2 (101)), 167-169.
28. Shodiyev Ziyodullo Ochilovich, & Shodiyev Nematjon Sadirovich. (2022). KINEMATIC STUDY OF FLAT BASE MECHANISMS. *E Conference Zone*, 61–69. Retrieved from <https://www.econferencezone.org/index.php/ecz/article/view/888>
29. Ochilovich, S. Z. (2020, September). Inoyatov Ikrom Shaxriloyevich, Shodiyev Ne'matjon Sadirovich. Tabiiy yaylovlar va uning bugungi kundagi ahamiyati. In *Эффективность применение инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве» международная научно-практическая онлайн-конференция* (pp. 25-26).
30. Musinovich, S. M. (2023, June). DRIP IRRIGATION INTENSIVE APPLE ORCHARDS AND SEASONAL WATER CONSUMPTION. In *Proceedings of Scientific Conference on Multidisciplinary Studies* (Vol. 2, No. 6, pp. 8-14).
31. Khamidov, M. K., Juraev, U. A., Buriev, X. B., Juraev, A. K., Saksonov, U. S., Sharifov, F. K., & Isabaev, K. T. (2023, February). Efficiency of drip irrigation technology of cotton in saline soils of Bukhara oasis. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1138, No. 1, p. 012007). IOP Publishing.
32. Sharifov Firdavs, & Mirzamurotov Mirshod. (2024). G'O'ZA O'SIMLIGINI YETISHTIRISHDA SUV TEJAMKOR SUG'ORISH TEKNOLOGIYALARINI QO'LLASH. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 461–464. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/98>